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COMMUNICATION AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN ORGANIC ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

Many organizations today are characterized by rigid bureaucracies with strict rules, well defined procedures, narrowly defined tasks and top-down communication, thereby promoting employee powerlessness, unproductive behaviours and poor organizational performance. This study therefore, examines the correlation between organic organizational structure and organizational performance. This is an analytical study which draws its data from secondary sources such as books, journals and internet. A close look at the model of organic structure reveals that the model is studded with many interesting characteristics which have direct positive correlation with employee's needs satisfaction and positive behaviours in the organization. Anchored on 9,9 (Team Management) of Blake and Mouton's Leadership Grid as the theoretical framework, the study builds on the assumption that high concern for both production and people in the organization has the tendency to foster positive employee's behaviours, maximize efficiency and attain goals. The study concludes that organic structure is fundamental to efficient functioning of an organization because of its flexibility and adaptability in nature. It is recommended, among others that approaches characteristic of organic organizational system be adopted in forward-looking organizations as there is a propensity to foster greater employee's positive behaviours and greater organizational performance and stability.

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